

Online Career Counseling in Scientific Research: Bibliometric Data Analysis

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KEYWORDS	ABSTRACT
Online Career Counseling ICT Bibliometric Analysis	Career counseling as a scientific field, adapted to the new, constantly changing demands of modern lifestyles and especially of the labor market, is called upon to integrate information and communication technologies into its services. In this context, international scientific research is investigating the emergence of online career counseling to recommend ways to improve practices and assist policymakers in making decisions. We explore and map international literature on issues related to online career counseling by searching the Scopus scientific database in titles, summaries and keywords of articles published from 2012 to 2022, for the terms “employment” or “job” or “occupation” or “profession” or “career” or “vocational” and “guidance” or “counseling” and “digital” or “internet” or “ict” or “online”. The analysis of the data led to conclusions about the scope of online career counseling, as well as the mapping of mainstream scientific trends and their change over time.
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Introduction

Career counseling, as a scientific field adapted to the constantly changing demands of modern lifestyles and especially of the labor market, is called upon to integrate information and communication technologies into its services (Brown & Lent, 2016; Harris-Bowlsbey & Sampson, 2005; Mallen et al, 2005).

Digital technology offers new possibilities in job search and in the cultivation of professional skills (Jansen, Jansen & Spink, 2005; Yu, 2012). Online counseling services primarily focus on utilizing information technology (IT) and the internet to offer career guidance. These services have become increasingly convenient and beneficial through the adoption of email, videoconferencing, and social media technologies. This technology has been used in a variety of contexts, including workforce development, entrepreneurship, career development, and learning development, to provide different ways of communication. According to research, online counseling is frequently utilized to improve social involvement and academic advancement (Pordelan et al., 2018). Professionals have incorporated these tools into their interventions. Specifically, they use online counseling, applications, automated tools, and social media platforms (Pordelan & Hosseinian, 2022).

In this context, international scientific research is studying the emergence of online career counseling to suggest ways to improve practices and to support policymakers in their decision-making (Burns et al., 2013)

In our research, we used bibliometric data analysis software to map the international scientific literature on issues of online counseling and career orientation, and to explore bibliometric data such as key authors, countries with most publications, keywords, articles with most citations, and other information that map scientifically the field. Our goal was to analyze the dominant trends that appear

in the international literature and their variation over time. Bibliographical data analysis tools support this study by exploring the prevalent patterns in the scientific space.

Methods

To attain these objectives, we searched in the scientific database Scopus, and in particular, in the titles, summaries, and keywords of articles published in magazines, conference volumes, and book chapters from 2012 to 2022, for the terms “employment” or “job” or “career” or “vocational” or “occupation” or “profession” and “guidance” or “counseling” and “digital” or “internet” or “ict” or “online”. The search returned 964 articles. The criteria for the final selection of articles were: The Exploitation of Technological Media and the Internet in the Advisory Process and a Focus on or Report on Professional Counseling. This criterion excluded articles that do not investigate issues of professional counseling (that is, counseling with the sole aim of improving mental health, for example) and those that do not include new technologies and the internet in professional counseling and guidance practices. The selection of the articles yielded a 123-article body to analyze.

Results

Table 1

Descriptive data

Description	Results
Main information about data	
Timespan	2012:2021
Sources (Journals, Books, etc)	96
Documents	123
Document types	
article	123
Document contents	
Keywords Plus (ID)	496
Author's Keywords (DE)	481
Authors	
Authors	375
Author Appearances	406
Authors of single-authored documents	19
Authors of multi-authored documents	356
Authors collaboration	
Single-authored documents	19
Documents per Author	0,328

Authors per Document	3,05
Co-Authors per Documents	3,3
Collaboration Index	3,42

As shown in Table 1, our data consists of 123 articles from 96 sources published from 2012 to 2021. The authors are 375, with an average of 3 authors per article. Table 1 shows all descriptive data, the main information such as the total documents, the time span, the type of files, the contents, data about the authors, and data about the cooperation between the authors.

Figure 1. Annual Scientific Production

As shown in Figure 1, the production of articles in the field of online counseling and career guidance from 2012, shows an upward trend starting from 5 articles, reaching 15 in 2016, and continuing steadily upwards from 2017, reaching 20 articles in 2020. After 2020, there seems to be a decrease, which we will be able to assess over the years, by studying whether the upward trend will continue, whether there will be a decrease in interest, or whether there will be stability in the publication of relevant surveys.

Figure 2. Average Article Citations per Year

The average number of bibliographical references per year is stable at 2–3 references per year. The scientific field of study is experiencing a small but steady increase in the trends of scientific publications (Figure 2).

Figure 3. Country Scientific Production

The countries with the greatest contribution to the subject's content are the United States and the United Kingdom, with Australia being the third most prolific country. Among the European countries, Germany displays a larger number of articles (Figure 3).

Figure 4. Corresponding Author's Country

As shown in Figure 4, Germany presents most of the partnerships between countries in the same publication. In the horizontal bars, the blue color corresponds to articles by authors from the same country, and the red color corresponds to articles in which more than one country collaborate.

Figure 5. Most Relevant Affiliations

While the USA and the UK are the most heavily annotated countries, the University of Isfahan in Iran has the extensive set of articles, followed by the National Central University in Taiwan. Universities from England, Spain, Germany, the USA, and Italy follow with 5 articles (Figure 5).

Figure 6. Most Relevant Sources

Figure 6 shows that the 123 articles were published in a total of 96 magazines, 2 of which have more than 3 articles on online counseling. The British Journal of Guidance and Counseling publishes the most articles on the issue.

Figure 7. Source Local Impact by H index

Figure 7 shows the 10 most important journals, ordered by H index. The H index is also used as a predictor for future research. Therefore, our results show that journals with the most citations are the British Journal of Guidance and Counseling, Education, and Information Technologies. The rates of the citations on the issue in the relevant journals are expected to remain high in the years ahead.

Figure 8. Most Relevant Authors

Figure 8 illustrates the main authors, i.e., the authors with the most publications on the subject being examined.

Figure 9. Author Local Impact by H index

The top five authors appear in the same order and in the same ranking according to the H index; authors Pordelan, Berking, Ebert, Lehr, and Riper come first in terms of their productivity and the impact of their publications, as they gather the most citations. Notably, Pordelan is affiliated with the Faculty of Education and Counseling at the University of Isfahan in Iran, while the other four authors come from the Faculty of Clinical Psychology and Psychotherapy of the University of Nuremberg in Germany (Figures 8- 9).

Figure 10. Top-Authors' Production over the Time

Figure 10 shows author productivity according to the number of publications and citations over time. The dark blue marks show the total number of publications per year, while the light blue marks show the total number of publications with the most citations per year. So, it seems that the most prolific authors published more articles in 2016, having more citations than in 2018 and beyond.

Figure 11. Collaboration Network

Figure 11 displays the network of collaborations between authors. The first two authors, Ebert and Berking, are mostly collaborating, as seen in the red team. The purple team shows the authors with whom Pordelan collaborated as the main author.

Figure 12. Most Global Cited Documents

Our analysis also showed the articles with the most citations (Figure 12). First in citations is the article titled "JobTIPS: A Transition to Employment Program for Individuals with Autism Spectrum Disorders," which studied the effectiveness of a training program in interview skills for people belonging to the autism spectrum. The intervention exploited the capabilities of the internet, such as augmented reality, video models, visual support, etc. The results of the survey indicated that young people aged 16–19 who participated in the program managed to develop more effective verbal skills (Strickland, Coles & Southern, 2013). The second article with 62 citations showed that e-coach intervention could be considered an effective treatment for work-related stress-related symptoms (Ebert et al., 2016). The next study, with 56 global citations, combines an online training program for health professionals with interactive simulations to develop, among other skills, effective cooperation in the workplace (Ellman et al., 2012). The following article is a survey conducted with an internet-based intervention aimed at managing stress in employees (Zarski et al., 2016). The fifth article explores the potential of digital technology to support adolescents in their career planning (Nota, Santilli & Soresi, 2016). So, it turns out that researchers are particularly interested in these directions. That is, stress related to work, the development of skills in different population groups, and support for young people in career issues.

Figure 13. Most Relevant Words

A total of 496 keywords were analyzed. The 30 most frequent of them are shown in Figure 13. There are over 20 occurrences of the keywords “female”, “internet”, “male”, “human”, “adult”, and “article”, while there are more than 10 occurrences of the words “humans”, “employment”, “adolescent”, “controlled study”, and “vocational guidance”. As a result, it appears that research regarding adolescents and adults predominates, while the interest revolves around people, as it should have been expected given the subject of the field of counseling.

Figure 14. Word Cloud

With the visual representation capability provided by the software that was used, we can present our findings through a word cloud visualization. Keywords that appear in a larger font mean higher frequency. We point out words related to people that appear more pronounced, while we can easily distinguish the frequency of words related to psychology.

Figure 15. Co-occurrence Network

Our analysis also allowed links to be established between all these terms; two main word groupings were formed. In the group shown in red color terms related to population groups are displayed, as well as terms such as "career," "work," and "career orientation". In the group shown in blue color terms and concepts that come from the area of psychology occurred, such as "mental health," "work stress," "stress management" and "counseling".

Figure 16. Trend Topics

In Figure 16, we can track the trend over time based on the keywords chosen by the authors. It seems that the term "career" began to emerge more frequently in 2020 and the term "vocational guidance" in 2019 in the articles that studied the integration of the Internet and technology into the counseling process. Research on youth dominated in 2015, and one year later, in 2016, research focused on groups of adolescents and middle-aged individuals. In 2017, the interest turned to adults and employment.

Figure 17. Thematic Evolution

From 2019 onward, there seems to be a shift in interest from people in general to more specific terms, like "students" and "vocational guidance" (Figure 17).

Figure 18. Conceptual Structure Map

Through Multiple Correspondence Analysis combined with Hierarchical Clustering, a conceptual map was created, showing three basic clusters of keywords. The sources of the data are the keywords of the articles, as well as terms that appear in their titles and summaries. “Young adults”, “adolescents” and “teachers, associated with “autism” and “professional rehabilitation”, along with “vocational guidance”, “e-counseling”, “career” and “professional orientation”, appear in the first cluster (blue). In the second cluster (red), there are “middle-aged

individuals” and “medical students”. They appear along with the terms “psychology”, “psychotherapy”, “internet”, “counseling”, “education”, and “economics”. In the third cluster (brown), the “employee” appears along with terms such as “depression”, “job stress”, “mental stress”, and “stress management” (Figure 18).

Figure 19. Thematic map

Word pair analysis creates clusters, which are considered as central themes. The density and centrality of clusters are utilized to categorize them and create a two-dimensional diagram (Aria & Cuccurullo, 2017). In the thematic map (Figure 19) that is created, we can analyze the issues according to the quartile in which they occurred. The upper right quadrant, with higher density and centrality, displays topics that are significantly related to the field under study and help build its conceptual framework. In this context, the words "controlled study", "psychology" and "major clinical study" appear as main topics in groups. Therefore, psychology seems to play a central role in articles studying online professional counseling, most commonly clinical and controlled studies. The category of the words "students," "economics," and "recommender systems" is also important. In most articles, where the research involves students, their preference between online and/or live professional counseling is discussed. Furthermore, the “human”, “article” and “female” word group appears between motor themes and basic themes. The issues with low density but high centrality in the lower right quadrant are the important issues that permeate the various aspects of the field. No word group in “Basic Themes” appeared in our analysis. The word "health" appeared in the quadrant where topics, that have not been largely analyzed and are less relevant to the field of professional counseling, are depicted; no keywords appeared in the upper left quadrant on topics with a higher degree of analysis, but less interest in the field under study.

Limitations

The limitations of our research concern the language, as only English-language research was studied. Also, the time frame was established as starting from 2012. Our data source was only the Scopus database, and the key words selected were restricted. To address these limitations, can supplement our study by future research that will be focused on the Web of Science, extending the examined period.

Conclusion

The analysis of bibliometric data has led to conclusions about the scope of online professional counseling as well as the mapping of mainstream scientific trends and their change over time. This analysis provides useful information to researchers and professional counselors, who wish to study the integration of new Internet technologies and services to carry out new field investigations, starting from the study of dominant trends.

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Η Διαδικτυακή Επαγγελματική Συμβουλευτική στην Επιστημονική Έρευνα: Ανάλυση Βιβλιομετρικών Δεδομένων

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Επαγγελματική Συμβουλευτική, Διαδίκτυο, Νέες Τεχνολογίες, Βιβλιομετρική Ανάλυση.	Η επαγγελματική συμβουλευτική ως επιστημονικό πεδίο προσαρμοζόμενο στις νέες, διαρκώς μεταβαλλόμενες απαιτήσεις του σύγχρονου τρόπου ζωής και ειδικότερα της αγοράς εργασίας καλείται να ενσωματώσει τις νέες τεχνολογίες της πληροφορικής και της επικοινωνίας στις υπηρεσίες της. Στο πλαίσιο αυτό η διεθνής επιστημονική έρευνα μελετά την εμφάνιση της διαδικτυακής επαγγελματικής συμβουλευτικής προκειμένου να προτείνει τρόπους βελτίωσης των πρακτικών που ακολουθούνται, αλλά και να υποστηρίξει τους φορείς πολιτικής κατά τη λήψη αποφάσεων. Στην παρούσα έρευνα αξιοποιείται λογισμικό ανάλυσης βιβλιομετρικών δεδομένων με σκοπό τη διερεύνηση και χαρτογράφηση της διεθνούς βιβλιογραφίας σε θέματα επαγγελματικής συμβουλευτικής με τη χρήση του διαδικτύου. Πιο συγκεκριμένα, αναζητήσαμε στην επιστημονική βάση δεδομένων Scopus και ειδικότερα, στους τίτλους, τις περιλήψεις και τις λέξεις κλειδιά άρθρων δημοσιευμένων από το 2012 έως 2022, τους όρους «απασχόληση (employment/ job/ occupation/profession)» ή «καριέρα (career)» ή «επαγγελματικός (vocational)» και «προσανατολισμός (guidance)» ή «συμβουλευτική (counseling)» και «ψηφιακός (digital)» ή «διαδίκτυο (internet)» ή «ΤΠΕ (ict)» ή «διαδικτυακά (online)». Η ανάλυση των δεδομένων οδήγησε στην εξαγωγή συμπερασμάτων σχετικά με το εύρος του πεδίου της διαδικτυακής επαγγελματικής συμβουλευτικής, καθώς και στην αποτύπωση των κυρίαρχων επιστημονικών τάσεων και της μεταβολής τους στον χρόνο.
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